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Vaijayantīkośa- Nature and Methodology

Athira.T¹

Introduction

One of the important features of Sanskrit language is the long tradition of lexicons. The early sources of this tradition of lexicons in Sanskrit language can be traced in the Vedic age itself. The *Nighaṇṭu* which is an exegetical annotation of obscure and difficult Vedic vocabulary, is the earliest known lexicon in Sanskrit. The date of its composition is assumed to be the last phase of Vedic age, viz. a period before the sixth century BCE. Thenceforth a large number of lexical works of different nature had been written in Sanskrit throughout the two and a half millennia. These lexicons bear a prominent place in the history of Sanskrit language and literature since they, in different ways, have helped the development of the language and its knowledge systems.

A new history of lexicography in Sanskrit begins with the entry of classical lexicons, especially with the composition of *Amarakośa*. Unlike *Nighaṇṭu* and *Nirukta*, it opens the epoch of comprehensive dictionaries in Sanskrit. There are so many lexicons written after *Amarakośa*, based on the style that *Amarasimha*, its author, presented. They are generally called 'Classical lexicons'. These are specially written for classical language.

In Sanskrit lexicons, *Vaijayantīkośa* (*Vaijayantī*) of Yādavaprakāśa (Yādava) is considered as the largest lexicon. It is very popular, and is well known in the name *Yādavīya*, among the prominent commentators like Mallinātha. Not only

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Mallinātha, many other lexicographers praised Yādava and his work *Vaijayantī*. Later lexicographers such as Hemacandra and Medinīkara while speaking about their predecessors' works, mention the name of *Vaijayantī* also.

Yādava, the author of *Vaijayantī*, introduced himself through some verses given in the end शुभाम् of his work. The verses are,

इति यतिवरसङ्घपूजिताङ्घ्रिः प्रथितयशा भुवि यादवप्रकाशः ।
 व्यरचयदभिधानशास्त्रमेतत् सह वचनैः सह लिङ्गसङ्ग्रहेण ॥
 एतां शुभामष्टभिरुक्तकाण्डैः भूतस्वरूपैरिव नाममालाम् ।
 दत्तं विशाले हृदये मुरारिस्ताम् वैजयन्तीमिव वैजयन्तीम् ॥
 एवं सुक्ष्मैर्न्यायनिर्णीतशब्दैः सर्वार्थानां व्यञ्जकोसौ निघण्टुः ।
 संविन्तीनां भूषणं सत्कवीनाम् प्राप्तः पारं वैजयन्तीनिघण्टुः ॥
 नानाविद्यावेद्यवाग्रजमाला मूर्तं वेदं वेदयन्ती त्रिवेद्याः ।
 रोदुं / बोदुम् बुद्धिध्वंसकध्वान्तचक्रं प्राज्ञैर्ज्ञेयं वैजयन्ती जयन्ती ॥

(Vaijayantikōśa Granthopasmhārah)

From this description it is learnt that the name of the author of *Vaijayantī* is Yādavaprakāśa, He is a follower of Vaiṣṇava cult and lived in Thanjavoor of Tamil Nadu. The birth of Yādava presumably was at the peak time of Vaiṣṇavism. He was a respected figure in Vaiṣṇava community. The south Indian origin of Yādava was justified by his usage of some words, which are rare in north India and popular in south India (Bühler 5).²

2 Based on the description supplied by Yādavaprakāśa in his *Vaijayantī*, G. Bühler, in his article 'Gleanings from Yādavaprakāśa's *Vaijayantī*' observes; "From this passage which, I should say, belongs to the author himself, it appears that the venerable Yādavaprakāśa was not only an ascetic, but probably held a high position in his order. For, if it is true that, as verse two asserts, his feet were worshipped by a multitude, or perhaps a community of Yati's, he must at least have been the head of a maṭha or monastic establishment. It may, however, be that he had attained a higher rank, that he was the head of a sect, or a jagadguru, as the modern Indian expression is. Verse 3 which recommends *Vaijayantī* to Murāri, shows further that the author was a Vaiṣṇava. In addition to this information we may gather from other passage of the Kōśa that Yādavaprakāśa's home let in southern India. He repeatedly alludes to or quotes works, studied chiefly or exclusively in the south, such as the *Taittirīya Āraṇyaka* and *Āpastambīya Gṛhyasūtra*. From the later work he extracts, as we shall see further on, the curious terms, describing the defects of maidens, which make them unfit to be wedded. Moreover he occasionally gives those Sanskrit words, which are peculiar to southern India. Thus he has instead of the common northern form *sukram*, the rarer one *suklam*, which the southern schools of the *Taittirīya śākhā*, the *Boudhāyanīya-s* and the *Āpastambīyas*, employ. The same passage mentions also the curious word *śrehu*, which Professor Stenzler has placed into

There is a verse which refers to Rāmānuja as the disciple of Yādavaprakāśa (Pathak 175). This disciple of Yādava started Vaiṣṇava sect, with the permission of him. It is well-known it was Rāmānuja who initiated the cult of Vaiṣṇavism in Tamil Nadu. So it is reasonably assumed that Yādava's disciple Rāmānuja and Rāmānuja who founded Vaiṣṇavism in Tamil Nadu are identical. In addition F. E. Hall in the appendix of his *Catalogue of Indian Philosophical Works*, mentions the work *Prapannāmṛta* authored by Rāmānuja, and furnishes the details of the personal life of Rāmānuja (Bühler 5). The information given by F.E Hall in it also justifies the conclusion that, both the Rāmānujas are one and the same. Rāmānuja's period of life is said to be 1017-1137 C.E. Hence, it may safely be said that Yādavaprakāśa was a follower of Vaiṣṇava cult and he was a senior contemporary of Rāmānuja. And it can be ascertained beyond doubt that Yādavaprakāśa lived in 11th century C.E.

Methodology of Vaijayantikośa

As has been mentioned earlier, *Vaijayantī* is the largest work among the classical lexicons. Its volume is two times larger than *Amarakośa*. The work is divided into two parts. *Paryāyakośa* (Synonymous Lexicon) and *Nānārthakośa* (Homonymous lexicon). The *Paryāyakośa* is further divided into five kāṇḍa-s. The number of adhyāya-s (chapters) in each kāṇḍa varies. The *Nānārtha* part is very popular. But *Paryāyakośa* is significant from the point of view of its methodology. The arrangements of words and other aspects of methodology followed by Yādava in general are similar to that of *Amarakośa*. The popularity and the acceptance of *Amarakośa* all over India is evident from this. Yādava tries to explain the details related to all words in a very precise format.

The name of the kāṇḍa-s and the adhyāya-s are based on the nature of contents described in each one. This arrangement of words is highly helpful to find out a word from the work. *Svargakāṇḍa*, *Antharikṣakāṇḍa*, *Bhūmikāṇḍa*, *Pātālakāṇḍa* and *Sāmānyakāṇḍa* are the names of kāṇḍa-s in *Paryāyakośa* part.

the text of the Gautamīya Dharmaśāstra (1.44) on the authority of the Telugu MSS. It may also be mentioned that southern commentators, such as Mallinātha and Kavindra Sarasvatī, quote *Vaijayantī* much oftener than e northerners, and that MSS. of the *Vaijayantī* are at present, it would seem, procurable only in the Dravidian districts."

Ekākṣarakośa, Dvyakṣarakośa and Tryakṣarakośa are the chapters of *Nānārthabhāga*. Each kāṇḍa has sub divisions also.

Svargakāṇḍa

The first kāṇḍa which is titled as Svargakāṇḍa comprises the words related to svarga. It has three divisions. They are Ādidevādhyāya, Lokapālādhyāya and Yakṣādhyāya. The names of adhyāya-s are enough to explain their contents.

Ādidevādhyāya

Being the first adhyāya of *Vaijayantī* it begins with a maṅgala. The maṅgala addresses Brahman.

ओङ्कारार्थाय तत्त्वाय वाच्यवाचकशक्तये ।

ब्रह्मसंज्ञाय पूर्वेषां गुरुणां गुरवे नमः ॥ (Paribhāṣādhyāya 1)

Here the word 'brahmā' used by the author indicates the creator-god Brahman and also śabdabrahman. After maṅgala the author explains the rules followed in the composition of his lexicon, in nine and half verses. They refer exclusively to the manner in which the gender is indicated or may be recognized in doubtful cases. Remarkable aspects are the abbreviations ṣaṇ for ṣaṇḍa and klī for klība both referring to the neutral gender.

Then the first adhyāya namely Ādidevādhyāya, listed the words related to Ādideva simply. The important deva-s like Brahman, Viṣṇu and Śiva are called Ādideva here. The author discusses the synonyms with the legend behind all the nouns. It makes the kośa very interesting to read and to remain easy-accessible for gathering information from it. Viṣṇu is said to have ten incarnations and Yādava considers each of the incarnations and provides synonyms for each one. Also the family and other related things of each deity are listed by the author. For instance, while explaining the synonyms of Viṣṇu, Yādava refers to his vehicle, weapon, living place etc.

कौस्तुभोस्य मणिलक्ष्म श्रीवत्सो नन्दकस्त्वसिः ।

चापशार्ङ्गम् पाञ्चजन्यशङ्खश्चक्रं सुदर्शनम् ॥

(Vaijayantikōśa, Ādidevādhyāya, 17)

Lokapālādhyāya

Here Yādavaprakāśa includes the names of deities like Indra, Agni, Varuṇa, Vāyu, Kubera, Yama etc. While describing the names and synonyms, Yādavaprakāśa furnishes other factors also that are

related to them.

Yakṣādhyāya

This adhyāya is the smallest adhyāya of Svargakāṇḍa. After discussing the names of main deities in the previous chapters, remaining are discussed here. Descriptions on minor deities and demigods such as Yakṣa, Kinnara and Gandharva etc. are the subject matter contained in it.

Yādava here treats the members of heaven in the order of their importance, features etc. So, first he includes the Trimūrti-s, then deva-s like Indra and Varuṇa. Thereafter Yakṣa, Kinnara etc. are depicted. Since the Yakṣa-s and Kinnara are not really gods, they are considered at the end of the list. These categories in fact are artists in heaven; some are singers, and some others are dancers. Yet they possess divine powers like the deva-s. That is why they are included in this category. Here the *Vaijayantī* follows the method of *Amarakośa* in general. The difference is that Amarasimha describes these categories in single varga.

Antarīkṣakāṇḍa

The second kāṇḍa in *Paryāyabhāga* of *Vaijayantī* is called Antarīkṣakāṇḍa. Here as the name indicates the author discusses the names of atmospheric things like clouds, sound and light. The fire or light (agni) is considered an atmospheric thing. *Nirukta* the commentary of *Nighaṇṭu* includes the agni as a prominent god in the group of Pṛthvīsthānīyadevatā (Earthly gods) (तिस्रः एव देवता, अग्निः पृथ्वीस्थानियः; Nirukta, II.7). The names of chapters in Antarīkṣakāṇḍa are Jyotiradhyāya, Meghādhyāya, Khagādhyāya and Śabdādhyāya.

Jyotiradhyāya

It is the largest adhyāya of Antarīkṣakāṇḍa. In this adhyāya author listed each and every divine thing in the atmosphere. Ākāśa, aṣṭadiś, digagaṇā-s, dvādasadvākara-s etc.

Meghādhyāya- Here Yādava gives the synonyms of cloud (megha) and some terms that are related with rain like ativrṣṭi and anāvṛṣṭi. It is the smallest adhyāya of Antarīkṣakāṇḍa.

Khagādhyāya- The birds are included in Anarīkṣakāṇḍa along with jyotis, śabda, and megha. Here the author first describes the synonyms of birds. Then he started to list almost all the flying things.

There is a long list of different birds such as haṁsa, cakravāka, baka, jalakāka, kukkuṭa, mayūra, kāka, ulūka, śārī, kapota and kokila. Then he includes the names of some arthropods like butterflies and mosquitoes. That is why this adhyāya is not an adhyāya of birds, it is a general adhyāya of flies.

Śabdādhyāya- It is the last adhyāya of Antariṣakāṇḍa. Author started the adhyāya through defining śabda. Then as usual the author gives the synonyms and related terms of śabda. Yādava tries to name the sound produced by animals along with the variations of sounds.

घोरितं तुरगादीनां नासापुटभवे ध्वनौ ।

तन्दनं रम्भणं रम्बा रम्भितं च गवां ध्वनिः ॥ (Śabdādhyāya, 5.)

Bhūmikāṇḍa

Bhūmikāṇḍa is the third kāṇḍa of *Vaijayantī*. It is the rich and elaborate kāṇḍa in *Vaijayantīkośa*. It contains many adhyāya-s, They are; Deśādhyāya, Śailādhyāya, Vanādhyāya, Paśusangrahādhyāya, Manuṣyādhyāya, Brāhmaṇādhyāya, Kṣatriyādhyāya, Vaiśyādhyāya, Śūdrādhyāya.

Deśādhyāya- Deśādhyāya comprises the names and synonyms of places. The author includes the names of many places such as Bhārata and Naiṣadha. Along with the names, the author provides the specialties (for what the place is famous for). The seven islands of Jambudvīpa (in which Bhārata was situated) the Lavaṇadvīpa (which is surrounded with ocean) etc. are described here. There are six Anudvīpa-s and the sub-Dvīpa-s for each. This adhyāya provides a general picture of Bhāratadeśa, and the regions situated around Bhārata. Here the Bhārata described by Yādavaprakāśa may be the Bhārata of 11th century CE. So the term country here means only a region.

Śailādhyāya

In this Adhyāya Yādava starts with the synonyms of mountain. Then as usual the author lists important mountains and their synonyms. In some cases he also provides the specialties of mountains. For instance the following verses may be cited;

मलये त्रिकालाषाढी विन्ध्यस्तु जलवालकः ।

हिरण्यनाभो मैनाकः सुदारुः परियात्रकः ॥

माल्यवांस्तु प्रस्रवणो हिमवांस्तु हिमालयः ।

राजताद्रीस्तु कैलासो हराद्रीर्महितश्च सः ॥

In these verses, Malaya, Vindhya, Maināka, Prasavaṇa, Himālaya, Kailāsa etc are the names of mountains. With the names sometimes the author provides the specialties of that particular mountain. Rajatādri is the synonym for Kailāsa and it indicates the colour of Kailāsa too.

Vanādhyāya - The third adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa, namely Vanādhyāya is very lengthy. As the name indicates the author describes the synonyms of trees Yādava provides other details of the trees, such as its fruit and flower.

पलाशे किंशुकः पर्णो वतपोथस्तिपर्णकः ।

कपित्थे स्युर्दधिफलो दधित्यग्राहिमन्मथाः ॥ (Vanādhyāya, 29)

The Vanādhyāya contains 235 verses.

Paśusaṅgrahādhyāya

The fourth adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa contains the names of animals. Synonyms of the animals continued with the list of animals starting with lion. The list includes pig, bull, deer etc. Here, the author provides the details like their habitat, their colour and habits. In some places, the myth related to the particular animal is also noted.

स्कन्धशृङ्गो यमरथः कटाहो दंशलालिकाः ।

हंसकालिसुतश्चाथ सृजया महिषोऽसितः ॥

गवलश्च परस्वांश्च महिषः स्यादरण्यजः ।

The number of verses in Paśusaṅgrahādhyāya is 74 and a half .

(Paśusaṅgrahādhyāya, 20).

Manuṣyādhyāya

As the name indicates the fifth adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa explains the synonyms and other details of human being. According to the author of *Vaijayantī*, humans are classified in groups based on their colour, work etc. Here humans are divided into four classes. Brāhmaṇa, Kṣatriya, Vaiśya and Śūdra. Then the author describing some special names for the children, born in inter-caste marriage. The names are different in all combinations. Yādava explains this topic in detail. The view of Yādava about the caste system in his society is apparent from this portion. It explicitly says that Yādava was a strict follower of the Brahmanical social system that was prevalent and prominent during his period. It may also be said that the author here strictly follows the rules laid down by the Dharmaśāstra texts. This adhyāya has 121

verses.

Brāhmaṇādhyāya

The sixth adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa discusses about Brāhmaṇa, the first category mentioned in the four-fold classification of human. This is done by Yādava following the tradition of Dharmasāstra. Initial traces of this classification can be seen in the later phase of Vedic period itself. Smṛti-s further developed this concept and they announce that this classification is made by Lord Brahman. Yādava starts the first verse of Brāhmaṇādhyāya as,

ब्राह्मणो मुखजो विप्रो भूदेवो मैत्र एताशः । (Brāhmaṇādhyāya, 1)

According to it Brāhmaṇa is born from the face of Lord Brahman. After giving the synonyms of Brāhmaṇa, the author explains the sixteen rituals to be observed in the life of a Brāhmaṇa, These are known as ṣoḍaśakarman-s and also ṣoḍaśasamskāra-s (sixteen ceremonies). Subsequently Yādava explains different duties and costumes of Brāhmaṇa-s. Descriptions about different types of preceptors (guru-s) and the reasons for their difference, types of vidyā-s, list of fourteen vidyā-s, etc. also are available in this part. It is one of the voluminous adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa. The number of verses in this chapter is 140. The author here states almost all aspects related with Brāhmaṇa category including their rituals, costumes, works, relationships etc.

Kṣatriyādhyāya

This adhyāya starts with the explanation of Kṣatriya as,

क्षत्रं बाहुजराजन्यौ भूशक्रः क्षत्रियो विराट् । (Kṣatriyādhyāya, 1)

Yādava here defines Kṣatriya by explaining the word 'kṣatram'. Along with synonyms of Kṣatriya he describes the duties, dressings, relationships, rituals etc. of Kṣatriya. Since the Kṣatriya-s are mostly supposed to be rulers, the author focuses on explaining the famous seven constituents related to the administration of a kingdom. These elements collectively are known as rājyāṅga-s Yādava writes,

स्वाम्यमात्यसुहृत्कोशराष्ट्रदुर्बलानि च ।

राज्याङ्गानि प्रकृतयः पौराणां श्रेणयोपि च ॥ (Kṣatriyādhyāya 3)

Here Yādava adheres to the Arthaśāstra tradition. According to this svamin- the king, amatya- ministers/counselors, suhṛt- allies, kośa- treasury, rāṣṭra- countryside, durga- the fortified city and bala- military power are the constituents of a country. Following this Yādava

explains aṣṭasampatti, śakatitraya, ṣaḍguṇa-s, aṣṭavargavardhana, saptamahāvyaasana-s, samādhimukhyopāya, kṣudropāyātraya, tantra, āvāpa and adṛṣṭa. This adhyāya is lengthier than Brāhmaṇādhyāya, and it contains 220 and a half number of verses.

Vaiśyādhyāya

The details of the third category of human, the Vaiśya, are dealt with in the sixth adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa. The author here also follows the same way of explaining seen in the previous chapters on Brāhmaṇa and Kṣatriya. The synonyms and other aspects related to Vaiśya such as their duties, costumes etc. are enumerated in this chapter. While describing the duties of Vaiśya, Yādava explicates the term vārtā which can be found in the Arthaśāstra of Kauṭilya, as one of the important area in which a ruler has to be well-versed. Vārtā, as is used in the Arthaśāstra, stands for kṛṣi, vāṇijya and paśupālana, which altogether represent the economic activities of a country. These three are the main areas in which a Vaiśya is supposed to get engaged. Yādava here too fully complies with the Arthaśāstra tradition.

Śūdrādhyāya

The seventh adhyāya of Bhūmikāṇḍa is discussing the fourth category of human. 141 and half of verses are there in this adhyāya. The Śūdra-s are mostly servants and working class. The hair cutting, rope work, pot making etc. are also considered as Śūdravṛtti- work of Śūdra-s. Yādava has enlisted all the works performed by Śūdra-s during his time and provides names for people based on their job. The antiquity of this system can be assumed from the fact that references to this are available in the Vedic lexicons also.³ Yādava here following his predecessors provides some additional information like the tools used for work, their outcomes etc.

चण्डिलः क्षुरमर्दी स्यान्नापितोऽन्तावसाय्यपि ।

क्षुरोऽस्य वपनं शस्त्रं कलिका कर्तनी कृवि ॥

कुम्बकारः कुलालोऽस्य पचनं पाकमण्डलम् ।

धूसरश्चाक्रिकस्तैलि पिण्याको ना खलिः स्त्रियाम् ॥

(Śūdrādhyāya, 26, 27.)

Here kṣura- shaving of air, is mentioned as one of the works of Śūdra. Katrikā is the instrument used in this work. In this manner, Yādava lists all the works and their tools. The works of Śūdra-s referred

3 The word 'kāru' in *Nirukta* is used to indicate the meaning of sculpture.

to here are the basic needs of society. However, from the point of view of the society of the day, it can be seen that all these works were not of value to the working class.

Pātālakāṇḍa

Sarīsrpādhyāya

Pātālakāṇḍa commences with the adhyāya named Sarīsrpādhyāya. The meaning of the word sarīsrpā is reptile. The author started the chapter with the synonyms of Pātāla. Then he turned to enumerate different snakes and their synonyms. In the list of synonyms some snakes are mentioned as kings. Here Yādava agrees with the myth of Puraṇa-s. Based on that he envisages a kingdom of snakes. In connection with the list of snakes, Yādava provides many details about certain snakes. The venom, the doctor of venom, snake-bite injury, the enemies of snakes like nakula (mongoose) etc. Besides the list of reptiles this chapter speaks of lizard (gaulī), scorpion (vṛścika), spider (lūtā), arthropod (ṣaṭpada), fish (matsya), cancer (karkaṭa), frog (maṇḍūka) etc.

Jalādhyāya

The second adhyāya of Pātālakāṇḍa is Jalādhyāya. As is clear from the title, it is dedicated to describing water and water bodies. Starting with the synonyms of water the author gives details of bodies like wells, ponds, rivers and oceans. Then Yādava enlists almost all important rivers in India. First he considered three major rivers that are believed to be divine. The Jāhnavī or Gangā, Devasindhu and Yamunā are three divine rivers. The list includes Narmadā, Godāvarī, Kṛṣṇā and so on. Here Yādava mentions the things related to water or water bodies such as sand and flowers grown in water.

Purādhyāya

Pura means city. Synonyms of cities, important cities like Sāketa, Dvārakā, Vārāṇasī, Mithilā, Hastinapura, Avantī, Vāraṇāvāta, Māhiṣmatī etc. Then the author categorises the places based on geographical elements and gives the details of their location and status as village and town.

प्रान्तरं ग्रामयोर्मध्यमुपपन्नं त्वन्तिकाश्रायः ।

पर्यन्तभूः परिसरः कटो ग्रामेयकः पुनः ॥(Purādhyāya, 17)

The text mentions the structure of that cities like their 'kavāṭa'

(entrance), way, buildings, forts etc.

वारिकूटो हस्तिमुखो नगरद्वारकुट्टके ।

गोपुरं तु पुरद्वारं दिक्तु निस्सारणं मुखम् ॥ (Purādhyāya 15)

In the cities there are so many buildings and most of them are named by the author. Buildings are commonly known as śālā-s. Yādava prescribes that there should be specific and permanent places for particular śālā-s in a city.

कुप्य शालातु संधानि पक्षि शाला कुनालिका ।

चतुरं हस्तिनां शाला वाजिशाला तु मन्दुरा ॥

Having explained the other details of cities Yādava discusses the city life. The arrangement of adhyāya-s here causes some ambiguity. It is interesting to note that Purādhyāya is included in Pātālakāṇḍa. The inclusion of Sarīṣpādhyāya, Jalādhyāya, Bhūtādhyāya in this kāṇḍa has a common logic for the same. The reptiles, water and bhūta-s are assumed to be living underground. But, the logic behind including Pura-s or cities in Pātālakāṇḍa is unclear. In the arrangement of topics in the work sometimes myth and in some other contexts reality are considered for the same. But in the case of including cities in Pātālakāṇḍa neither myth or reality seems to support it.

Bhūtādhyāya

It is the last adhyāya of Pātālakāṇḍa. The very term 'bhūta' here denotes all living beings. The living things are classified into four groups based on their origin. They are jarāyuja, aṇḍaja, svedaja and udbhija. The first category of jarāyuja consists of human beings and animals. Birds and snakes are included in the group of aṇḍaja, mosquito and louse belong to svedaja category and the whole varieties of plants fall in the last category of udbhijja. The gender difference of humans is also taken into account by Yādava in this part. The adhyāya comprises 146 and a half verses.

Sāmānyakāṇḍa

This is a comparatively small kāṇḍa of *Paryāyabhāga*. The author divides this kāṇḍa into four adhyāya-s. The Gaṇādhyāya, Dharmakarmādhyāya, Guṇādhyāya, Arthavallīṅgādhyāya are the four adhyāya-s that constitute this kāṇḍa.

Gaṇādhyāya

As the name indicates, this adhyāya tells about 'gaṇa-s' or groups.

The groups of things and individuals have specific names. For example,

माणवानां तु माणव्यं बाडव्यं तु द्विजन्मनाम् ।
राजन्यकं मनुष्यकं राजकं च पृथक् पृथक् ॥
गार्भिणं यौवनं तासां गाणिक्यं गणिकागणे ।

(Gaṇādhyāya, Sāmānyakāṇḍa, 7,8)

Dharmakarmādhyāya

Dhātu-s or verb-roots are itemized here with their function and their respective verbal form. Defining the sense of dhātu is commonly done in a single way; either by root or by its function. This method is almost similar to the etymological (yaugika) and conventional (rūḍha) explanation of words given by Naiyāyika-s.

Guṇādhyāya

This adhyāya discusses the sensory information mainly based on five sense organs. The information from sensory organs is named as 'guṇa'. The number of guṇa-s in this way is five. They are; śabda (sound), sparśa (touch), rūpa (vision), rasa (taste) and gandha (smell). At first the author discusses the five sensory information in general, and subsequently explains each sensory information in detail. That includes the discussion of vision of visual images, colours etc.

शुक्ले शुभ्रशुचिश्वेताः पुण्ड्रको धवलोर्जुनः ।
अवदातः सितो गौरो विशदश्चेतपाण्डुराः ॥
रोहितो लोहितो रक्तो हारिद्रे पीतपीतले । (Guṇādhyāya,10,11)

The sound or śabda is described by Yādava as,

सत्यं तथ्यममृतं सम्यक् समीचीनं तथार्थवाक् । (Guṇādhyāya,3)

Arthavallīngādhyāya

The adhyāya begins as follows,

गुणयुक्तं क्रियायुक्तम् द्रव्ययुक्तं च वक्ति यः ।
स शब्दो वाच्यवल्लिङ्गो बालो वक्ता धनी यथा ॥ ⁴

The summary of the whole adhyāya is described in this verse. The author here enlists the nouns with their specialties, their root and the matter to which they are associated. Here Yādava informs that the speaker is a boy.

Nānārthabhāga

⁴ The words that refer to a quality, an action, or matter are listed in this chapter. The speaker is a boy. 'बालो वक्ता'

The Nānārthabhāga includes three kāṇḍa-s, the Dvyakṣarakāṇḍa, Tryakṣarakāṇḍa and Śeṣakāṇḍa. These kāṇḍa-s are arranged in a uniform methodology. The Dvyakṣarakāṇḍa and Tryakṣarakāṇḍa have equal number of adhyāya-s. The adhyāya-s are named as Strīliṅgādhyāya, Pulliṅgādhyāya, Napuṃsakaliṅgādhyāya, Arthavalliṅgādhyāya and Nānāliṅgādhyāya. Although Śeṣakāṇḍa also follows the same sequence of adhyāya-s, four adhyāya-s are added additionally in it in order to include the words that are not enumerated in other groups. The additional four adhyāya-s are Paryāyasamyoganyāyapradarśanādhyāya, Anekārthāvyayādhyāya, Avyayaparyāyādhyāya and Liṅgasṅgrahādhyāya.

Conclusion

Yādavaprakāśa's *Vaijayantīkośa* is an immediate follower of *Amarakośa*. In determining the gender and in the arrangements of words, the influence of *Amarakośa* is obvious in this work. Akin to *Amarakośa*, in the scheme of explanation of words, Yādava too follows Purāṇa-s and Dharmasāstra-s on many contexts, especially in the case of the words related with religious and ritualistic practices.

Among the two parts of *Vaijayantī*, viz. *Paryāyabhāga* or Synonyms part and *Nānārthabhāga* or the homonyms part; the latter (homonyms) bears more importance than the earlier one (synonyms). Most of the manuscripts of *Vaijayantī* contain only the part of homonyms. Also the commentators, especially south Indians, quoted verses from this portion only. This informs the popularity of homonym lexicon in southern India. German Indologist and Sanskrit Professor Gustav Salomon Oppert who published an edited version of *Vaijayantī* in 1893 states that he used eleven manuscripts to prepare his new edition of the text and only a single manuscript alone had contained the whole text.⁵ He also says that the one and only manuscript that comprised the whole text was in Malayalam script.

5 "I have used eleven MSS. (A, B, C, D, E, F, G, H, I, J, K and L) for this edition of *Vaijayantī*. A is the only MS- which contains all the eight kāṇḍas complete. It is written in Malayalam characters and belongs to the library of H.H. the Ciria Anujan Rāa of Paḍiññāre Kovilakam near Calicut, as quoted in the first volume of my 'Lists of Sanskrit Manuscripts in Private Libraries of Southern India'. I obtained it through the assistance of Mr. W. Logan, late Collector of Malabar."- G. Oppert, Preface to *Vaijayantīkośa*, pp.6.

Vaijayantī has some significant features which distinguish it from other early and mediaeval lexicons available in Sanskrit. It is the most voluminous work among classical lexicons. This is the kośa that contains the greatest number of Vedic words. Scholars like M.M. Patkar finds this as a significant reason for the merit and authority to *Vaijayantī* (Patkar 60). An important point to be noted here is that since the complete text of this kośa was found in only one manuscript, the words and descriptions in it are uncertain or doubtful in very many contexts in the edited work. Another remarkable fact to be stated in this regard is that the scholars including G. Oppert and Hargovind Sastri, who took effort to publish *Vaijayantī*, have declared that neither they could notice any commentary of this text nor any reference to a commentary on it has come across their attention.

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